

Generating function of periodic sequences with eligible cycle.

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Choose the k and m values and apply the corresponding operation.

$$\begin{aligned} m &\in \mathbb{Z} \\ k &\in \mathbb{N}. \end{aligned}$$

$$f(k) = \begin{cases} m \text{ even} & \begin{cases} k \text{ even} & (k-m)/2 \\ k \text{ odd} & (3k+1+m)/2 \end{cases} \\ m \text{ odd} & \begin{cases} k \text{ even} & (3k+1+m)/2 \\ k \text{ odd} & (k-m)/2 \end{cases} \end{cases}$$

Each result is the value of k for the next iteration.

For all k , a sequence is generated that reaches $k_n = 1-m$ and ends in a cycle with $k_{(n-1)} = 2-m$.

Some examples of values of m and k_n :

$m = 1$	$k_n = 0$	for all	$k > 0$	
$m = 0$	$k_n = 1$	“	$k > 0$	
$m = -1$	$k_n = 2$	“	$k > 1$	For negative m , $k > -m$
$m = -2$	$k_n = 3$	“	$k > 2$	“ “ “
...	...		...	
$m = 2,$	$k_n = -1$	“	$k > 0$	
$m = 3,$	$k_n = -2$	“	$k > 0$	
$m = 4,$	$k_n = -3$	“	$k > 0$	
$m = 5,$	$k_n = -4$	“	$k > 0$	
...	...		...	

Examples:

A sequence will reach the number 11, if $m = -10$ and will enter the cycle with $2-m = 12$.

The function is applied for even m :

$$\begin{cases} k \text{ even} & (k-m)/2 \\ k \text{ odd} & (3k+1+m)/2 \end{cases}$$

$$f(k) = 85, 123, 180, 95, 138, 74, 42, 26, 18, 14, 12, 11, 12, 11 \dots$$

Calculations:

$$\begin{aligned}(85 * 3 - 9) / 2 &= 123 \\ (123 * 3 - 9) / 2 &= 180 \\ (180 + 10) / 2 &= 95 \\ (95 * 3 - 9) / 2 &= 138 \\ (138 + 10) / 2 &= 74 \\ (74 + 10) / 2 &= 42 \\ (42 + 10) / 2 &= 26 \\ (26 + 10) / 2 &= 18 \\ (18 + 10) / 2 &= 14 \\ (14 + 10) / 2 &= 12 \\ (12 + 10) / 2 &= 11 \\ (11 * 3 - 9) / 2 &= 12 \\ (12 + 10) / 2 &= 11 \\ \dots\end{aligned}$$

Example with $k = 1149$ and $m = 5$. The cycle will be $2-m = -3$ and $1-m = -4$:

The function is applied for odd m :

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{ll} k \text{ even} & (3k+1+m)/2 \\ k \text{ odd} & (k-m)/2 \end{array} \right.$$

Calculations:

$$\begin{aligned}(1149 - 5) / 2 &= 572 \\ (572 * 3 + 6) / 2 &= 861 \\ (861 - 5) / 2 &= 428 \\ (428 * 3 + 6) / 2 &= 645 \\ (645 - 5) / 2 &= 320 \\ (320 * 3 + 6) / 2 &= 483 \\ (483 - 5) / 2 &= 239 \\ (239 - 5) / 2 &= 117 \\ (117 - 5) / 2 &= 56 \\ (56 * 3 + 6) / 2 &= 87 \\ (87 - 5) / 2 &= 41 \\ (41 - 5) / 2 &= 18 \\ (18 * 3 + 6) / 2 &= 30 \\ (30 * 3 + 6) / 2 &= 48 \\ (48 * 3 + 6) / 2 &= 75 \\ (75 - 5) / 2 &= 35 \\ (35 - 5) / 2 &= 15 \\ (15 - 5) / 2 &= 5 \\ (5 - 5) / 2 &= 0 \\ (0 * 3 + 6) / 2 &= 3 \\ (3 - 5) / 2 &= -1 \\ (-1 - 5) / 2 &= -3 \\ (-3 - 5) / 2 &= -4 \\ (-4 * 3 + 6) / 2 &= -3 \\ (-3 - 5) / 2 &= -4 \\ \dots\end{aligned}$$

$$f(k) = 1149, 572, 861, 428, 645, 320, 483, 239, 117, 56, 87, 41, 18, 30, 48, 75, 35, 15, 5, 0, 3, -1, -3, -4 \dots$$

A sequence generated with $k = 1154$ and $m = 0$. Its cycle is with $2-m = 2$ and $1-m = 1$:

The function is applied for even m : $\left\{ \begin{array}{ll} k \text{ even} & (k-m)/2 \\ k \text{ odd} & (3k+1+m)/2 \end{array} \right.$

Calculations:

$$1154 / 2 = 577$$

$$(577 * 3 + 1) / 2 = 866$$

$$866 / 2 = 433$$

$$(433 * 3 + 1) / 2 = 650$$

$$650 / 2 = 325$$

$$(325 * 3 + 1) / 2 = 488$$

$$488 / 2 = 244$$

$$244 / 2 = 122$$

$$122 / 2 = 61$$

$$(61 * 3 + 1) / 2 = 92$$

$$92 / 2 = 46$$

$$46 / 2 = 23$$

$$(23 * 3 + 1) / 2 = 35$$

$$(35 * 3 + 1) / 2 = 53$$

$$(53 * 3 + 1) / 2 = 80$$

$$80 / 2 = 40$$

$$40 / 2 = 20$$

$$20 / 2 = 10$$

$$10 / 2 = 5$$

$$(5 * 3 + 1) / 2 = 8$$

$$8 / 2 = 4$$

$$4 / 2 = 2$$

$$2 / 2 = 1$$

$$(1 * 3 + 1) / 2 = 2$$

$$2 / 2 = 1$$

...

$$f(k) = 1154, 577, 866, 433, 650, 325, 488, 244, 122, 61, 92, 46, 23, 35, 53, 80, 40, 20, 10, 5, 8, 4, 2, 1 \dots$$

Sequences with $m = 1$, will reach the the number $1-m = 0$.

$$f(k) = 38, 58, 88, 133, 66, 100, 151, 75, 37, 18, 28, 43, 21, 10, 16, 25, 12, 19, 9, 4, 7, 3, 1, 0.$$

Sequences with $m=1+1=2$, will reach the the number $1-m=-1$.

$$f(k) = 782, 390, 194, 96, 47, 72, 35, 54, 26, 12, 5, 9, 15, 24, 11, 18, 8, 3, 6, 2, 0, -1.$$

Sequences with $m=1+n$, will reach the number $1-m=-n$.

$$f(k) = 971, 436, 704, 1106, 1709, 805, 353, 127, 14, 71, -14, 29, -35, -67, -83, -91, -95, -97, -98.$$